

A REVIEW OF PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE OF ORGANIC PRODUCERS ABOUT THE ADOPTION OF ORGANIC FARMING

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Abstract:

Organic food consumption has increased significantly in both developed and developing countries. Organic food accounts for a small percentage of the food market, but its rapid expansion has attracted the interest of consumers, businesses, and researchers. In this regard, we should increase the organic produces. This paper presents a review of a recent Indian researcher's article on the perception and attitude of Indian organic cultivators about the adoption of organic farming. A total of thirty-four articles that met our criteria were found and used for this paper to look for studies within the period from 2010 to 2019.

Key Words: Attitude, Conventional, Organic Certification, Perception, Sustainability

Introduction:

Conventional farming farmers are used High-yielding varieties, along with irrigation water, chemical fertilizer, and pesticides. This mix of high-yielding production techniques has helped the country generate a food surplus while also contributing to soil health, pollution, pesticide toxicity, and agricultural production sustainability challenges [32]. In 2009, the majority of farmers converting to organic farming, as a result, their socio-economic situation improved [5].

Marketing and government policy elements were shown to be the most important in affecting all types of farmers, regardless of their educational level, social considerations were more important to farmers with more farming experience [4]. This paper is reviewed on the perception and attitude of Indian organic cultivators about the adoption of organic farming.

Materials and Methods:

This article review of a recent Indian researcher's article on the perception and attitude of Indian organic cultivators about the adoption of organic farming. A total of thirty-four articles were found and used for this paper within the period from 2010 to 2019.

Perception on Organic Farming:

The overall perception of producer, and also marketer, consumer of organic products channel members organic food was superior in quality than conventional foods, the appearance of organic food was considered inferior to conventional [25]. The farmers were aware that 'integration of crop and livestock will decrease the production cost as inputs can be derived easily', 'organically grown food tastes better', 'more nutritious', 'certification of an organic farm is primarily based on documentation [3].

The farmer's attributes like education, social participation, economic motivation, annual income, source of information, contact with extension personnel, innovativeness, and risk orientation were found to hold a positive and strong relationship with their perception about sustainable organic farming practices [15]. They have a favorable opinion of organic farming [21]. Organic cultivation was found superior to conventional cultivation in relation to increased human employment, low cost of cultivation, more profits, enhanced input use efficiency and reduced risk; boost self-reliance and livelihood security of the farmers. Moreover, organic cultivation has a positive impact on human health, soil conservation and water holding capacity, increased biomass, maintain pH value, soil aeration and fertility [17].

Organic farming has a bright future [7]. The crops grown by the organic producer Vegetables and greens followed by oilseeds and only a few are farming other crops such as flowers and medicinal plants [7].

Demography of Organic Producers:

Age, educational background, farm size, benefits, social factors, and impression of organic farming all had significant associations on organic farming attitudes [21] Majority of the producers were men [9], and younger age [30] [31] also age group of above 65 years [9], and well educated [9] [31] having larger landholdings [30] [31] and in the income level of INR 3-4 lakhs [9].

Although, conventional producers identified production and marketing barriers as the main constraints to adopting organic farming, while the age and education of the farmer have not deemed a problem [20].

The category of certified organic farmers majorly belonged to the old age category, had possessed collegiate education, acquired an annual income up to rupees one lakh. fell under the big farmer category and had a low level of farming experience in organic farming. They were practicing a mixed cropping pattern followed by double cropping and mono-cropping, where depending on bore well as a primary irrigation source. They have attended more than three training in organic farming, possessed a medium level of mass media exposure and had a medium level of extension agency contact [22].

Attitude of Organic Producers:

The majority of organic farmers had a favorable view toward organic farming operations of vegetable cultivation. More than 90% of organic and conventional farmers agreed that using organic agricultural practices was critical to improving vegetable quality. Almost all conventional farmers have reduced their chemical application over time and increased their use of organic manures. The majority of them had a good attitude about organic vegetable cultivation [18]. The organic, as well as conventional farmers, believed that the use of organic farming practices was essential for a better quality of vegetables [18].

Knowledge Level of Organic Producers:

Organic farmers had more knowledge than inorganic farmers. Innovativeness, market orientation, extension orientation, and mass media exposure all demonstrated a strong link with organic farmers' knowledge level [14]. Although, They had a high to medium level of knowledge about organic farming [10] [16].

The characteristics like innovativeness, market orientation, extension orientation and mass media exposure were significant with the knowledge level of organic cultivators. Profile characteristics of organic and inorganic cultivators, namely, age, social interaction, economic motivation, market orientation, environmental protection and belief in organic farming also had a significant and positive impact on knowledge level except for economic motivation which had negative persuade on knowledge about organic cultivation [17].

Age, education status, farm experience were not significantly correlated with knowledge of farmers showing the positive effect of the approach in overcoming individual barriers. Farm size, number of bearing and non-bearing palms, the intensity of intercropping, trainings attended, social participation, extension contact, extension participation and mass media exposure were significantly correlated with farmers' knowledge [2]. Also, less knowledge about organic cultivation practices and lack of knowledge about fund availability from the government [16].

Reason for Adoption of Organic Farming:

The five primary factors including economics, social, marketing, cultivation, and governance influence organic farming adoption. Furthermore, based on their demographic classification, such as education level, farm size, farming experiences, and land ownership [4]. The motivated factors were "to protect the fertility of the soil", followed by "to protect the environment", and "for better health", to adopt organic tomato cultivation [6]. Health and safety, environmental, Ideological and philosophical and economic motivations are the most important motivating factors mentioned by rice producers [9].

Adoption/Conversion Factors of Organic Farming:

Organic farming training has a significant impact on the transition to organic farming [15] [27]. The years under conversion were positively associated with reduced input costs and with increased income and increased yield [20]. The perceptions and attitude have significant effect on intention on organic farming, knowledge and practice about organic farming also have a significant impact on people's willingness to move to organic farming [29]. Also, the "Market and economic" factors are most important followed by "Government support" and "Environmental" [19].

Organic Farming Practices and Level of Adoption:

Organic farming rely on animal manures, green manures, crop rotations, crop residues, legumes, off farm organic wastes, and aspects of biological pest control to keep soil productivity and tilt, to support plant nutrient and to control insects, weeds and other pests [26].

Doing multiple cropping because it provides fair and stable return, protects soil fertility and cyclical farming is possible. Few of them cultivating Single cropping for the reason of including crop suitability for the region, high demand for the crop, lack of knowledge regarding multiple cropping, and favorable crop price [7].

Most of farmers have a high level of knowledge about organic farming procedures. There are significant information gaps in organic farming approaches such as the usage of Ha NPV, tricho cards, bio-pesticides, and NADEP compost [24].

Vermicompost and Mulching was found to high extent of adoption. Compost, Green manuring, Liquid manure and River bed soil reflecting medium extent of adoption of respondents are found to be adopters [26]. Majority of respondents belonged to medium extent of adoption in organic sugarcane cultivation practices category [16] [26]. Good and very high extent adoption of organic farming practices will definitely help in agriculture production [26].

Sustainability of Soil:

Agricultural and food production challenges, organic farming provides viable methods of maintaining and building healthy soil [26]. Overall, soil quality improved in terms of physical, chemical, and biological

qualities, as well as the availability of macro and micronutrients, indicating improved soil health and crop production sustainability in organic farming systems [34]. Organic farming improves soil fertility and profits in the long run [28].

Pricing Strategies:

The organic producers have followed some price-fixing strategies for their produces. They fix their own prices, followed by using the market price, use the price set by the association. And use a cost-plus strategy, followed by price their crops based on demand, and price their crops based on market forces/intermediaries [7].

Marketing of Organic Produces:

Marketing issues of the organic producers. 'Unavailability of an earmarked marketplace/shop for organic crops' as their main source of concern [33]. Uncertain storage facility for a long time affects the Supply Chain leads to Industrial Sickness followed by the acceleration in globalization and trade restrictions. The problem in processing the value-added organic products is a Lack of technically expertise equipment followed by raw material storage which affects the supply chain [8]. They were felt a 'lack of government support for organic market development [5].

Government Policy and Certification:

Organic farming land certification is expensive and a burden on farmers [11] [13]. The difficulty in obtaining organic certification was the biggest issue that organic growers encountered in production [1]. Without government support, the adoption of organic agriculture seems to be a highly demanding task in a situation, where the majority of the farmers fall under the small and marginal group [4] [23].

Suggestion:

Earning a fair profit is good planning followed by multiple cropping and substitute crops and the least importance is specified for using modern technologies [7]. Simultaneously they should also be educated on the procedures of organic cultivation, standards certification and labeling. Extension machinery may also be geared up, to supply quality organic inputs required for organic vegetable cultivation [18]. Hence, to promote organic farming in a developing country like India, the government has to introduce more schemes where farmers should get exclusive training and support to strengthen their plan behind the adoption of organic farming [4] [23]. Organic farming requires effective planning and implementation of various measures and also support from the Government and the Universities for the growth of organic farming as well as to attract more farmers to switch over to organic farming practices [12].

Conclusion:

Positive perception of organic farming with significant relationships between age, educational background, farm size, benefits of organic farming, and social factors. The organic farmers had a favorable attitude towards organic farming practices. The overall perception of producer organic food was superior in quality, the appearance of organic food was considered inferior to conventional foods. The five primary factors including economics, social, marketing, cultivation, and governance influence organic farming adoption. Organic farmers had more knowledge than inorganic farmers. Obtaining organic certification was the biggest issue that organic growers encountered in production. Organic cultivators are sold their produces by own fixed prices, followed by using the market price. Without government support, the adoption of organic agriculture seems to be a highly demanding task in a situation, where the majority of the farmers fall under the small and marginal group. To promote organic farming in a developing country like India, the government has to introduce more schemes where farmers should get exclusive training and support to strengthen their plan behind the adoption of the organic farming.

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